

Sustaining climate action: towards synergy politics for durable political support

November 2025

Funded by European Union's Horizon
Europe Programme under Grant
Agreement No. 101094551

Key messages

- **Climate policies fail politically when they worsen living standards** and durable ambition requires making the transition an improvement in affordability and access to essential services.
- **Integrated policy packages** combining climate action and social protection achieve faster decarbonization and reduced inequalities. They ensure stronger political support than carbon taxation or growth-based strategies alone.
- **Fair and visible redistribution of climate revenue** is indispensable: households must see clear, near-term and local benefits to transitioning.
- **Job Guarantees, universal access to low-carbon mobility and affordable housing** are key to preventing territorial backlash and maintaining trust in the transition.
- **Synergy politics** - pursuing climate ambition in ways that improve everyday livelihoods and well-being of people - offers a plausible route for the EU to achieve an ecologically effective, socially just and politically durable transition

Background & Context

Europe has entered a turning point for climate politics. After years of ambitious announcements and an internationally praised Green Deal, political support for climate action is becoming increasingly fragile. Energy price shocks, social inequalities, war, and rising inflation have shifted priorities for many policymakers. As for households, in several Member States, climate policies have become synonymous with rules imposed “from above” (restrictions on cars, costly renovations) rather than a promise of better lives. Even citizens who acknowledge the climate emergency can oppose policies when they fear losing jobs, mobility, or purchasing power.

What is happening is not a rejection of climate action as such. Public-opinion data have consistently documented rising levels of concern among Europeans regarding global warming, biodiversity loss, and other environmental risks. The backlash we observe among certain population groups is rooted in another sentiment: the fear of unfair sacrifices. Households already struggling to pay rent, heat their homes, or keep their car on the road can perceive climate policies as additional burdens. Rural and small-town residents feel left behind by

metropolitan-centred transitions. Workers in carbon-intensive regions experience decarbonization as a threat to their social and economic security and identity. This geography of perceived “green losers” is an unquestionable fuel for political opposition. Moreover, climate action has been framed by some actors as an ideological issue rather than a societal necessity, further reinforcing rejection among certain groups.

This reveals a deeper issue: the European transition has been presented in public debates through the lens of trade-offs. **Policymakers frequently describe climate action as something we must endure for future generations.** The public debate is structured around questions such as “how much growth are we ready to sacrifice to save the planet?”, “how many jobs will disappear in the automotive or fossil sectors in the name of ending fossil fuel exploitation?”, or “how high can carbon prices rise before the climate effort becomes unbearable?”

This framing locks climate policy into a zero-sum logic: more climate action equals less social protection and less prosperity. It treats living standards as collateral damage of decarbonization. The political economy

implications are clear, as climate ambitions become vulnerable: every shock (inflation, recession, pandemic, electoral shift) can justify the slowing down or rolling back of commitments. This dynamic has been witnessed in the last few years across the European Union: reactions against fuel taxes, pushback on building renovation policies, suspensions of environmental standards.

At the same time, **the green transition is increasingly shaped by distrust**. Citizens doubt that the financial and industrial benefits of the green shift will be widely shared. They observe that subsidies often support corporations first and households only eventually, if at all. They see profits in renewables rise, while their own bills increase. Groups who feel ignored become receptive to narratives accusing climate policy of serving “urban elites”, “Brussels bureaucrats”, or “foreign competitors”. As organized opposition to climate action gains political traction, advocates of more ambitious measures often appear fragmented and defensive.

Yet the risk of political fragility is not inevitable. **The problem lies less in the objectives of climate protection than in the way they are delivered**. When climate policy is experienced as improving people’s daily life, such as cleaner air, cheaper transport options, secure jobs, or warmer homes, support becomes stronger and more resilient. What undermines climate policies is not the ambition itself, but the absence of a social foundation that protects people throughout the transition.

Europe therefore needs a profound reframing of the way it thinks about the ecological transition. Rather than presenting decarbonization as a burden, climate action must prove its usefulness for households and communities, making it a just transition where climate and social action go hand in hand. **The debate must move from “how much prosperity must we give up to save the climate?”, to “how can climate action directly improve people’s daily lives?”**

This means embracing what we call synergy politics: designing policies that secure both ecological sustainability and the living standards of European citizens. In synergy politics, the key performance indicator is not just emissions reduction, but also whether households can meet their essential needs in mobility, housing, food, and energy without falling into insecurity regarding those needs being met.

This shift is crucial for political durability. An ecological transition that worsens inequalities will struggle to survive electoral cycles. A transition that lowers constrained spending for households and expands access to essential services will become a source of political support. By acknowledging everyday material concerns and embedding social protection at the heart of climate action, Europe can transform today’s fragile politics of trade-offs into a stable, majority-backed politics of synergies.

SPES evidence

Building on comprehensive Eurobarometer survey data (2003-2023), the SPES project has analyzed changes in public concern for the environment and explored to what extent economic challenges and crises have led to shifts in attention. Overall, the data shows that public concerns about the environment and climate change have grown steadily in Europe. In the early 2000s, only a small share of Europeans saw environmental issues as a top priority. Today, about one in four do. These changes are closely tied to economic conditions. During the financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, worries about jobs, prices, and the economic outlook rose sharply, and environmental concerns temporarily fell. When the pressures eased, attention to climate and environmental risks rose again.

The data also show major differences in environmental concern levels across Europe. People in North-Western European countries tend to show higher levels of concern, supported by stronger environmental institutions, higher incomes, and long-standing political debates on climate issues.

In parts of Southern and Eastern Europe, economic insecurities and different political agendas often lead people to prioritise other issues. These differences show that intra-European local contexts play an important role in shaping what citizens see as urgent. Further analyses show that economic shocks in a region tend to push environmental issues down the priority list, while extreme weather events can make them more salient. This reflects a simple reality: people have limited capacity to worry about many issues at once. Understanding these trade-offs in public perceptions can help policymakers design climate strategies that remain credible and supported even during times of economic stress.

To better understand what makes climate transitions politically viable, the SPES project has developed a new modelling tool calibrated with EU27 data: SEN-HARP, an agent-based, stock-flow consistent model designed to simulate not only carbon emissions and economic activity, but also how households live through the transition, and how they react politically. The model follows hundreds of

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households, diverse firms and banks, and a European government implementing different policy strategies.

Three key social and political mechanisms are integrated into the analysis. First, we track whether each household can meet essential needs such as food, heating and domestic energy, mobility and housing. This “needs satisfaction” indicator reveals whether the transition is experienced as a gain in tangible conditions of living. Second, the model incorporates regional and sectoral restructuring: the decline of fossil-dependent industries and the uneven access to public services create different local experiences of the transition, shaping the geography of support or resistance. Third, voting behaviour is modelled explicitly. Support for climate policies evolves as households experience their consequences. When costs concentrate on specific categories of households, anti-transition parties gain electoral advantage and can reverse policies in the next cycle.

Together, these mechanisms reflect a fundamental political reality: climate policies do not operate in a vacuum. In western countries, democratic support partly determines whether they endure long enough to be effective - while the example of China shows how political drive alone can safeguard a long-run green investments strategy.

The first major result from SEN-HARP is that climate strategies relying primarily on carbon taxation are extremely fragile, while redistribution of tax revenue can mitigate energy poverty and strengthen public support. Carbon taxes and price-based measures produce visible costs very early in the process: higher fuel and energy bills, reduced mobility for rural households, and immediate trade-offs in household budgets. Living standards decline before low-carbon alternatives become widely available. As a consequence, support for climate ambition collapses. Elections bring to power coalitions promising to halt or reverse the transition. In these scenarios, policies fail politically well before they succeed in terms of climate targets. France’s carbon tax induced Yellow

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Vests movement in 2018 exemplifies that.

The second finding concerns growth-based Green Deal strategies. Scenarios reflecting current EU approaches, built on green investments and technological substitution generate clear positive outcomes: more green jobs, lower emissions, and stronger innovation dynamics. Yet these benefits remain unevenly distributed. High-skill and urban households reap most of the gains, while others face persistent economic insecurity or increasing constrained spending. Inequalities in income and wealth distribution and need satisfaction persist or widen. Support for climate action remains high initially but erodes over time as segments of the population feel excluded from the benefits, threatening political durability.

The third finding demonstrates that climate ambition becomes resilient when embedded in an integrated social protection framework. The most successful scenarios combine green industrial investment with direct mechanisms protecting household security: a Job Guarantee for workers affected by restructuring, redistribution or universal transfers to stabilize purchasing power, and large-scale investments in affordable public transport and housing. In these settings, the majority of households see immediate improvements in their needs satisfaction.

Inequalities fall despite industrial transformations, and political support strengthens rather than erodes. Ambitious climate policy becomes self-reinforcing.

Finally, the scenario delivering both the fastest emissions reduction and the most cohesive social outcomes is one that can be described as a post-growth policy package. Universal access to essential services such as housing, mobility and energy reduces constrained spending and enhances resilience. Households rely less on energy-intensive consumption to maintain living standards. Well-being becomes less dependent on economic growth. People feel more secure as the economy decarbonizes, not less.

The overarching conclusion of the SPES evidence is clear: climate transition succeeds politically only when it improves people's daily lives. If households must sacrifice security and dignity, they will oppose the transition. If climate policy becomes a source of new rights and better living conditions, the public will defend it and political majorities will sustain it across electoral cycles. SEN-HARP shows that moving from the politics of trade-offs to genuine synergy politics is not idealistic, but a demonstrably, pragmatic and viable pathway to durable and ambitious climate action in European democracies.

Policy recommendations

01.

Expand universal access to **low-carbon essential services.**

Reducing household exposure to volatile energy and transport prices is a precondition for political stability in the transition. A European programme for Universal Basic Mobility should ensure reliable and affordable access to low-carbon transport: expansion and modernization of rail, capping fares for regional commuting, zero-fare public transport in vulnerable areas, and shared mobility solutions outside large cities. Public utilities should guarantee a protected block of low-carbon electricity at stable prices for all households. Supporting agroecological food systems might strengthen food security while reducing emissions. Together, these provisioning systems lower constrained spending, reduce inequalities, and transform climate policy into a direct improvement of daily life.

02.

Provide **job security and economic conversion** in transitioning sectors.

Preventing social shocks in regions dependent on fossil-intensive sectors is essential to avoid backlash. A European Job Guarantee should secure employment during industrial restructuring, offering stable wages and socially valuable work (energy retrofits, ecosystem restoration, care services, rail maintenance). Sectoral re-skilling programmes must be co-designed with unions and territorial authorities, ensuring workers can shift into green roles without loss of identity or income. Industrial policy should focus on green conversion of value chains (electric mobility, circular construction materials, renewable maintenance), backed by long-term public procurement commitments. Local “just transition pacts” close to France’s regional CoPs (Communities of Practice) can anchor these transformations in communities historically tied to carbon-based industries. The outcome is a transition where no community is sacrificed, fostering a broad and durable political coalition.

03.

Ensure **climate fairness** through visible and trusted **redistribution mechanisms**.

Redistribution cannot be seen as an afterthought to climate policy but as a condition for its legitimacy. Climate revenues should support universal climate dividends or automatic allowances for energy and housing, calibrated to income levels but designed to avoid administrative burdens that create stigma or low take-up. Protection must be upfront, not compensatory after hardship occurs. The Social Climate Fund is a first example of such a mechanism. Linking redistribution to expanded public services ensures long-lasting impacts on inequality and insulation against energy shocks. In practice, climate policy should enable households to live better and not just pollute less. As fairness is visible and tangible, climate action is less likely to become a source of resentment. The design of these redistribution mechanisms as well as the destination of the funds should be established and chosen through place-based and community-based decision making - municipal budgets being one example of that.

04.

Guide public and private investment with **quantity-based climate governance**.

Current reliance on prices alone creates uncertainty and perceived unfairness. Europe should move toward planned, gradual stranding of the most carbon-intensive assets, with clear schedules and negotiated support for affected workers and regions. Financial regulation and public banking tools must orient credit toward green capital formation and away from fossil lock-ins, ensuring that financing follows the transition pathway rather than hindering it. The EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy is a step in this direction. For example, the EU could combine a timetable for phasing out internal combustion engine car production with preferential lending for electric bus manufactures, while co-financing regional rail infrastructure that offers a practical mobility alternative. Such integrated coordination ensures that local populations see new opportunities emerging before old ones disappear. Financing could be guaranteed by the European Central Bank (ECB) and alternate fiscal policy schemes such as a modern Treasury Circuit.

05.

Reorient welfare systems toward need-based social security.

Europe's welfare architecture remains too dependent on high employment and economic growth, making the transition politically fragile as the economy stagnates or shrinks. The EU should develop a framework for Universal Basic Services for housing, mobility, healthcare and digital access that lowers dependency on private consumption to meet essential needs. An EU directive on adequate minimum income guarantees that no household falls below a decent living standard during restructuring. Tax and fiscal reforms should protect low-income households while constraining unsustainable behaviour at the top of the income distribution. This reconfiguration paves the way for a decoupling between prosperity and economic growth. By securing the social foundations of well-being, climate policies can become the new cornerstone of the EU's social contract.

06.

Overcoming austerity and the fear of public debt.

The transition cannot unfold under the constraint of fiscal orthodoxy. Europe must overcome the fear of public debt that has limited public investment since its inception. Public spending is the backbone of financial stability: sovereign bonds constitute the safest collateral for financial markets, particularly on repo markets. Constraining their issuance thus undermines financial stability. Rather than repeating a never ending austerity strategy, the EU should allow for massive national and mutualized bond issuance in coordination with the European Central Bank through quantitative easing. A renewed Treasury circuit, allowing governments and public banks to finance strategic projects directly, would strengthen fiscal-monetary coordination and guarantee more predictable flows of liquidity, de-financialising part of the member States' public debt. These steps should be the firsts to be implemented to make the above recommendations real.

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This Policy Brief was written by

Pierre Funalot, Bordeaux University, Bordeaux School of Economics; Roman Hoffmann, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Wittgenstein Centre for Demography and Global Human Capital (IIASA, OeAW, University of Vienna), Laxenburg, Austria; Jonas Peisker, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Wittgenstein Centre for Demography and Global Human Capital (IIASA, OeAW, University of Vienna), Laxenburg, Austria; Eric Rougier, Bordeaux University, Bordeaux School of Economics; Maïder Saint Jean, Bordeaux University, Bordeaux School of Economics.

Peer reviewers

Mario Biggeri, University of Florence; Jacopo Cammeo, European University Institute, Tiziano Distefano, University of Florence, Andrea Ferrannini, University of Florence, Sanna Honkaniemi, Social Platform.

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Funded by European Union's Horizon
Europe Programme under Grant
Agreement No. 101094551

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